

"EFFECT OF DIFFERENT PLANT GROWTH REGULATORS ON YIELD AND QUALITY OF SWEET ORANGE (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck)",Dakhore Pratiksha¹, Shivaji Shinde² and Santosh Barkule³¹M.Sc.(Horticulture) Scholar, Department of Horticulture, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.pratikshadakhore01997@gmail.com²Associate Professor, Department of Horticulture, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtrashivshinde72@gmail.com³Assistant Professor, Department of Horticulture, VNMKV, Parbhani, Maharashtrasrbarkule@gmail.com

(MS Received: 26.11.2023; MS Revised:30.12.2023; MS Accepted:01.01.2024)

MS 3150

(RESEARCH PAPER IN HORTICULTURE)

Abstract

The present investigation entitled with, "Effect of different plant growth regulators on yield and quality of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck)" was carried out during the year of 2022-2023. The results of present study indicated significant difference with respective of yield, quality and monetary returns among the different treatments tried. The yield parameters viz. number of fruits at harvest (315), fruit weight (215.76 g), yield per tree (68.02 kg) and yield per ha (188.40 q) were observed in treatment T₃ CPPU @ 3 ppm. The quality parameters viz. the maximum TSS (10.22 °Brix), ascorbic acid (54.48 mg/100ml), reducing sugar (4.46 %), non-reducing sugar (3.03 %), total sugar (7.49 %) and minimum acidity (0.39 %) noticed in treatment T₃ CPPU @ 3ppm. The treatment T₃ improved economics of Sweet Orange. In general, foliar application of CPPU @ 3 ml/lit was found beneficial for enhancing yield and quality of sweet orange Cv. Nucellar under Marathwada region of Maharashtra.

Keywords: Citrus, CPPU, Quality, Yield**Introduction**

The sweet orange, or *Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck, is a member of the Rutaceae family. It is grown in tropical and subtropical climates all over the world. The principle growing states for sweet oranges are Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Punjab, Haryana, and Rajasthan. The principal edible portion of a citrus fruit is the juice present in the juice vesicles. Commercial pectin and essential oils are made from the rind of the citrus fruits. The noteworthy medicinal research reveals that eating citrus can reduce risk of heart attack and strokes. The inner white peel and the rag of oranges when consumed along with the juice, it helps to relieve constipation, serving as laxative. The chemical composition of sweet orange shows that it contains water (89.2 %), sugar (58 %), pectin (1-2 %), glycosides (0.1-1.5 %), pentosans (0.8-1.2 %), citric acid (0.4 to 1.5 %), fibre (0.6-0.9 %), proteins (0.6-0.8 %), fat (0.2-0.5 %), minerals (0.5-0.9 %) and essential oils (0.2-0.5 %) and TSS (10-12° Brix) (Syed *et al.*, 2012). Nutrient deficiency disturbs the production of plant growth regulators which controls the size, colour and premature fruit drop. Excessive premature fruit drop is also dependent on 3 other factors like high temperature and water deficits, insect/pest attack, and wind velocity of the area (Ashraf *et al.*, 2015). Use of plant growth regulators along with micronutrients have a significant effect to improve quality of citrus fruits (Singh and Misra, 1986). As the fruit size in early stage is very small, the dropping is minimal. However, it is very severe when fruits are of medium size and whole area under citrus is covered with dropped fruits. The application of plant growth regulators is effective in reducing the excessive premature fruit drop. Plant growth regulators like 2,4 dichlorophenoxyacetic acid (2,4-D) and salicylic acid (SA) have been reported to be effective in controlling fruit drop in citrus (Ashraf *et al.*, 2015). Other plant growth regulators which are being used to prevent fruit drop include 2,4,5 trichlorophenoxypropionic acid (2, 4, 5-TPA), naphthalene acetic acid (NAA), and gibberellic acid (GA) (Michael *et al.*, 1999). Similarly, deficiency of micronutrients (Zn, Cu, Fe, and Mn) in the soil of citrus orchards also affects the fruit yield, quality and fruit drop (Ashraf *et al.*, 2015). Foliar application of Zn can improve the citrus fruit yield and quality and control the premature fruit drop (Ashraf *et al.*, 2015). The triacontanol has potential function in regulating and modifying various physiological processes in plant and enhancing flowering yield (Angrej Ali *et al.* 2021). The application of KNO₃ found to be best management strategy for getting higher quality production and productivity and it

can be beneficial for effective and economic management practices for sweet orange (Sable *et al.* (2022)). The N-(2-Chloro-4-pyridyl)-N-phenylurea (CPPU) is a very active cytokinin-like plant growth regulator that encourages chlorophyll production, cell division, and cell expansion. It also promotes the fruit set and quickens fruit growth (Zeng *et al.* 2016). Different workers suggested that application of suitable combination of plant growth regulators, macro and micro-nutrients can control the excessive fruit drop and improve the yield and quality of citrus fruit (Debbarma *et al.* 2016). Hence the present investigation employing selection of appropriate plant growth regulators, their quantity and method of application was undertaken with an objective to find out effect on yield and quality in sweet orange.

Materials And Methods

A field experiment entitled "Effect of different plant growth regulators on flowering, fruit set, yield and quality of Sweet Orange (*Citrus sinensis* L. Osbeck)" was conducted at Central Nursery Scheme, Vasantrao Naik Marathwada Agricultural University, Parbhani during the year 2022-2023. The experiment was laid out in 10 years old Nucellar sweet orange orchard with the tree spacing of 6×6 m consists of 9 treatments with 3 replications in RBD. The foliar application of different plant growth regulators at unopen bud stage, full bloom stage and fruit set stage. A manuring dose of 20 kg farmyard manure +15 kg neem cake and fertilizer dose of 800g N: 400g P₂O₅: 400g K₂O per tree was applied in two split doses. First half dose of nitrogen along with full doses of P₂O₅ K₂O and FYM+15 kg of neem cake was applied at second irrigation after stress in January and second half dose of nitrogen was applied 45 days after first dose. The treatments were as follows: . T₁- GA₃ @ 100 ppm, T₂- NAA @ 100 ppm, T₃- CPPU @ 3 ppm, T₄- Salicylic acid @ 100 ppm, T₅- Triacontanol @ 500 ppm, T₆- Boron @ 0.2 %, T₇- ZnSO₄ @ 0.5%, T₈- KNO₃ @ 0.1%, T₉- Control. Data obtained on various variables of yield and quality of fruits were recorded, analyzed by analysis of variance of randomized block design as suggested by Panse and Sukhatme, 1995

Results And Discussion

The perusal of the data presented in Table 1 regarding yield and quality of sapota fruits as influence by different plant regulators are discussed below.

Fruit weight (g)

The effect of different plant growth regulators on fruit weight of sweet orange are presented in the Table 1. The effect of different plant growth regulators on fruit weight of sweet orange was found significant value. The maximum fruit weight (215.76 g) observed in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) whereas, the minimum fruit weight (179.11 g) was observed in the treatment T₉ (Control). Foliar application of CPPU @ 3 ppm significantly increases the weight of fruits. It might be due to ample supply of metabolites which helps in growth and development, increases cell size and is also responsible for the production and transport of plant sugars that increased the weight of fruit. The results were found similar with Barkule *et al.* (2018) in sapota, Smith (2008) and Rafaat *et al.* (2012) in grapes and Mostafa *et al.* (2020) in avocado.

Total number of fruits at harvest

The highest number of fruits per plant (315 fruits) was observed in treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) which was found at par with treatment T₁ (300.67 fruits), treatment T₈ (299 fruits) and treatment T₂ (297 fruits) and treatment T₇ (294 fruits). While the lowest number of fruits per plant is recorded in T₉ (control) (258.67 fruits).

The significantly increase in number of fruits per plant due to the spraying of CPPU @ 6 ppm might be because it affects fruit set, fruit retention, fruit growth, and fruit development, which causes a greater quantity of large-sized fruits to mature and be ready for harvest, similar results were found by Barkule *et al.* (2018) in sapota, Khot *et al.* (2015) in grapes and Nimbolkar *et al.* (2015).

Yield of fruit per plant (kg)

Among the treatments, the treatment T₃ CPPU @ 3 ppm showed the maximum yield (68.02 kg) which was at par with treatment T₈ and T₁. Whereas the treatment T₉ control treatment showed the minimum yield (46.34 kg) among all treatment. This might be because of CPPU encourage cytokinin-induced mobilization (positively the movement of nutrients from other parts of plant to leaves) which ultimately helps in increasing production of more photosynthates. Similar finding is noted by Barkule *et al.* (2018) in sapota and Khot *et al.* (2015) in grapes.

Yield of fruit per hectare (q)

The data disclosed that, the application of treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) counts the highest yield of fruit per hectare (188.40 q) however, the minimum yield of fruit per hectare (128.36 q) was observed with T₉ control treatment. The increase in fruit volume might be attributed to stimulation of cell division by CPPU. Increased fruit mass and volume might be due to increased cell division and fruit expansion, production ultimately helps in increasing. These findings are supported by the results obtained by Bhat *et al.* (2011) in grapes.

TSS (Total Soluble Solid) (%)

It is evident from the data those different treatments exhibited significant differences among themselves in respect of total soluble solid of the fruit due to application of different plant growth regulators. The data shows that the significantly maximum total soluble solid (10.22 %) was recorded in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm). While minimum fruit total soluble solid (8.05 %) was recorded from control (T₉). This could be caused by the growth of more leaves, each of which contains considerably more chlorophyll, increasing the quantity of metabolites produced by photosynthesis and speeding up the movement of photosynthetic products (mostly carbohydrates) towards fruits. The observations similar to findings were reported by Barkule *et al.* (2018) in sapota, Malshe *et al.* (2020) in Mango and Supe and Marbhal (2008) in pomegranate.

Acidity (%)

The data shows that the minimum acidity (0.39%) was recorded in the treatment of CPPU @ 3 ppm (T₃) which was statistically at par with treatments T₁ (GA₃ @ 100 ppm) (0.42%), while maximum acidity (0.70%) was recorded from control (T₉). The lower titratable acidity

due to CPPU might be due to the metabolic changes with fast conversion of organic acids into sugars and their derivatives by the reactions involving reversal of glycolytic pathway or be used in respiration. The present findings are in agreement with those reported by Kim *et al.* (2006) in apples, Rafaat *et al.* (2012) in grapes, Fathi *et al.* (2011) in persimmon fruit.

Ascorbic acid (mg/100ml)

The data pertaining to ascorbic acid as influenced by different plant growth regulators are depicted in Table no 1. It is evident from the data those different treatments exhibited significant differences among themselves in respect of ascorbic acid of the fruit due to application of different plant growth regulators. The data showed that the maximum ascorbic acid (54.48 mg/100 ml) was recorded in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) while minimum ascorbic acid (38.48 mg/100 ml) was recorded from control T₉. The ascorbic acid content found higher in treatment T₄ (CPPU @ 6 ppm); it may be due to production of higher metabolites in tree which sent towards developing fruits ultimately increase content of ascorbic acid in fruits of treated tree. Similar results were also obtained by Barkule *et al.*, (2018) in sapota, Kumar *et al.*, (2013) in grapes, Suhathiya and Singaravel (2010) in tomato.

Reducing sugars (%)

The data showed that the maximum per cent reducing sugar (4.46 %) was recorded in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm) while minimum reducing sugar (3.58 %) was recorded from treatment T₉ (control). The results were in conformation with results of Supe and Marbhal (2008) in pomegranate. Reducing sugar was boosted by CPPU foliar spray because the starch was converted to sugars more quickly and was transported into the fruits.

Non-Reducing sugars (%)

The data pertaining to non-reducing sugar as influenced by different plant growth regulators are depicted in Table no. 1. It is evident from the data that different treatments exhibited significant differences in respect of non-reducing sugar of the fruit due to application of different plant growth regulators. The data disclosed that the maximum percent non-reducing sugar (3.03 %) was seen in the treatment T₃ (CPPU @ 3 ppm), while minimum percent non-reducing sugar (1.92 %) was recorded from treatment T₉ (control). This trend could be due to hydrolysis of starch during ripening resulting in accumulation of sucrose. The results obtained in the present investigation are in close conformity with those of Barkule *et al.*, (2018) in sapota.

Total sugars

The data pertaining to total sugars as influenced by different plant growth regulators are depicted in Table no.1. It is evident from the data the different treatments exhibited significant differences in respect of total sugar of the fruit due to application of different plant growth regulators. The data shows that the maximum percent total sugar (7.49 %) was recorded in the treatment of CPPU @ 3 ppm (T₃), while minimum percent total sugar (5.34 %) was recorded from control treatment (T₉). The possible explanation might be due to faster movement of simple sugars into fruit and cell expansion by CPPU as it increases cell size and is also responsible for the production and transport of plant sugars that increased. Thus, ultimately increases the total sugar Barkule *et al.* (2018) in sapota.

B:C ratio

The data regarding benefit: cost ratio of sapota was influenced due to application of different plant growth regulators. The highest cost of cultivation was (Rs 152340) observed in treatment T₃ *i.e.*, CPPU @ 3 ppm. The lowest cost of cultivation (136336) was reported in T₉ *i.e.*, control. Regarding the economic returns, the highest gross returns (Rs 621735.92) and highest net income (Rs 469395.44) was reported in T₄ *i.e.*, CPPU @ 3 ppm. Lowest gross returns (Rs 423594.59) and lowest

net income (Rs 287258.39) was found in treatment T₉ i.e., control. The similar findings were reported by Barkule *et al.*, (2018).

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Table 1: Effect of different plant growth regulators on yield and quality of sweet orange

Tr. No.	Treatments	Fruit weight (g)	Total number of fruits tree	Yield /tree (kg)	Yield /ha (q)	TSS (%)	Acidity (%)	Ascorbic acid (mg/100 ml)	Reducing sugars (%)	Nnon-Reducing sugars (%)	Total sugars (%)	B:C ratio(Rs)
T ₁	GA ₃ (100 ppm)	210.04	300.67	63.17	174.98	9.12	0.42	52.70	3.99	2.81	6.88	2.75
T ₂	NAA (100 ppm)	203.18	297.00	60.32	167.08	8.65	0.51	49.88	4.43	2.30	6.74	2.90
T ₃	CPPU (3 ppm)	215.76	315.00	68.02	188.40	10.22	0.39	54.48	4.46	3.03	7.49	3.08
T ₄	Salicylic acid (100 ppm)	196.12	285.67	56.02	155.18	8.52	0.60	40.89	3.93	2.14	6.36	2.66
T ₅	Triaccontanol (500 ppm)	199.28	289.67	57.74	159.94	8.55	0.56	45.60	4.39	2.27	6.66	2.73
T ₆	Boron (0.2%)	200.32	287.00	57.56	159.43	8.55	0.55	41.05	4.37	2.14	6.52	2.74
T ₇	ZnSO ₄ (0.5%)	201.12	294.00	59.21	164.00	8.62	0.63	46.30	4.41	2.30	6.70	2.85
T ₈	KNO ₃ (0.1%)	204.22	299.00	61.05	169.11	9.02	0.45	52.20	4.45	2.37	6.82	2.96
T ₉	Control	179.11	258.67	46.34	128.36	8.05	0.70	38.48	3.58	1.92	5.34	2.11
S.E m. ±		3.68	8.29	0.25	2.34	6.48	0.02	0.56	0.10	0.04	0.19	
C.D. at 5 %		11.08	24.94	0.74	7.05	19.52	0.05	1.69	0.29	0.11	0.57	